

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Authoring the Pathway Crosswalk Table

Procedures for describing relationships between pathways (blood vasculature, lymph vasculature, and peripheral nervous system).

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Introduction

The procedures outlined in this document describe how to create and extend the [pathway crosswalk table](#), which lists relationships between “pathway” based anatomical structures—blood vasculature, lymph vasculature, and peripheral nervous system (PNS). These include pathways that are “adjacent_to” each other (e.g., neurovascular bundles) and pathways that are “connected_to” each other (e.g., capillaries at the terminal end of arterial blood flow connected to venules that begin the flow of blood back to the heart). Note that this table is different from the pathway-organ crosswalk tables, which relate pathway based anatomical structures to anatomical structures in the nested partonomy tables (see the VCCF Section Overview for more details). The primary audiences for this SOP are the authors and reviewers of the pathway crosswalk table.

Roles and Responsibilities

The **Reviewer** is a domain expert in an organ, in blood vasculature, in lymph vasculature, or PNS, who reviews relevant portions of the tables and suggests corrections.

The **Table Author** is responsible for managing the content of the crosswalk table.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
Reviewer	Ilias Ziogas Fahim Imam	ziogasili@gmail.com fahim.imam@queensu.ca
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Procedures

Table Metadata: First 10 Rows

Similar to other HRA tables, the first 10 rows of the pathway crosswalk table are reserved for metadata. Row 1 contains the name of the table "Pathway Crosswalk". Row 2 is intentionally left blank. Rows 3-10 include information about the authors, reviewers, general reference publications, the DOI of the table, and the date and version of the table. For details about rows 3-10, see the SOP on [Authoring ASCT+B Tables](#).

Table Columns

Each row in the tables contains a single relationship between two structures, where each structure is an Anatomical Structure listed in any of the three Pathway-based ASCT+B tables—blood vasculature, lymph vasculature, or PNS.

Below please find a list of columns and their descriptions.

Table 2. Column descriptions for the pathway crosswalk table.

Column	Description
Structure1Name	The name of the first anatomical structure (pathway). This should be an existing anatomical structure in the blood vasculature, lymph vasculature, or PNS ASCT+B tables.
Structure1ID	The ID of the first anatomical structure (pathway).
Structure1Type	The type of the first anatomical structure. Possible values include "artery", "arteriole", "capillary", "venule", "vein", "lymph vessel", and "nerve".
Relationship	The relationship between the two anatomical structures (pathways). Values include "adjacent_to" and "connects_to".
Structure2Name	The name of the second anatomical structure (pathway). This should be an existing anatomical structure in the blood vasculature, lymph vasculature, or PNS ASCT+B tables.
Structure2ID	The ID of the second anatomical structure (pathway).
Structure2Type	The type of the second anatomical structure. Possible values include "artery", "arteriole", "capillary", "venule", "vein", "lymph vessel", and "nerve".

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Review process

- Confirm that the format of the table follows the SOP.
- Confirm that the Pathway IDs (Structure1ID and Structure2ID) appear in one of the three pathway ASCT+B tables (blood vasculature, lymph vasculature, and PNS).
- Confirm that the relationships are correct.
- Notify the Table Authors of any potential problems found.

References and Resources

- Boppana A, Lee S, Malhotra R, Halushka M, Gustilo KS, Quardokus EM, Herr BW 2nd, Börner K, Weber GM. Anatomical structures, cell types, and biomarkers of the healthy human blood vasculature. *Sci Data*. 2023 Jul 19;10(1):452. doi: 10.1038/s41597-023-02018-0. PMID: 37468503; PMCID: PMC10356915.
- Börner K, Teichmann SA, Quardokus EM, Gee JC, Browne K, Osumi-Sutherland D, Herr BW 2nd, Bueckle A, Paul H, Haniffa M, Jardine L, Bernard A, Ding SL, Miller JA, Lin S, Halushka MK, Boppana A, Longacre TA, Hickey J, Lin Y, Valerius MT, He Y, Pryhuber G, Sun X, Jorgensen M, Radtke AJ, Wasserfall C, Ginty F, Ho J, Sunshine J, Beuschel RT, Brusko M, Lee S, Malhotra R, Jain S, Weber G. Anatomical structures, cell types and biomarkers of the Human Reference Atlas. *Nat Cell Biol*. 2021 Nov;23(11):1117-1128. doi: 10.1038/s41556-021-00788-6. Epub 2021 Nov 8. PMID: 34750582; PMCID: PMC10079270.
- Weber GM, Ju Y, Börner K. Considerations for Using the Vasculature as a Coordinate System to Map All the Cells in the Human Body. *Front Cardiovasc Med*. 2020 Mar 13;7:29. doi: 10.3389/fcvm.2020.00029. PMID: 32232057; PMCID: PMC7082726.

Glossary

Anatomical structures: Parts of the body in defined locations and regions, including the surface, internal organs and tissues. These structures may be described by gross or microscopic morphology and include functional tissue units and highly organized cellular ecosystems (such as alveoli in the lungs).

ASCT+B Tables: Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers (ASCT+B) Tables are authored by multiple experts across many consortia. Tables capture the partonomy of anatomical structures, cell types and major biomarkers (e.g., gene, protein, lipid or metabolic markers).

Pathway: The paths through the body formed by blood vasculature, lymph vasculature, and PNS.

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